

Associating Outcome Measures across Chemical and Surgical Experimental Models of Chronic Osteoarthritis

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Abstract: The disease of osteoarthritis (OA) can be associated with persistent joint pain and disability. Numerous factors may contribute to the pain severity and also to the progression of OA, both of which may have different mechanistic pathways that could be targeted to develop treatments. However, in OA and OA-pain research, there are no accepted 'gold standard' OA models and associated outcome measures. Relatively little work has evaluated both the disease of OA and pain across different models. Therefore, we describe alterations in somatosensory processing, limb use, and joint degeneration in two rodent models of OA. Stifle (knee) OA was induced in Sprague–Dawley rodent via intraarticular injection of monoiodoacetate (MIA) or surgical transection of anterior cruciate ligament and destabilization of medial meniscus (ACL+DMM or DMM alone). To investigate OA-associated pain, whether evoked or spontaneous, a battery of reflexive and non-reflexive assays were employed. Joint degeneration was assessed histologically. Six-weeks post OA-induction, the ACL+DMM had higher lameness scores ($p < 0.001$) and tended to demonstrate greater functional disability with movement-induced and spontaneous (i.e., standing) impairments than MIA. However, joint degeneration was more severe in the MIA model with total loss of articular cartilage than ACL+DMM and 14 weeks post- DMM surgery. The findings here suggest that the ACL+DMM model may be more valuable in pain studies investigating changes in pain behaviors. Conversely, the MIA model may be a more suitable model for quickly screening novel therapeutics targeted towards mitigating or reversing histological changes associated with OA.

Keywords: osteoarthritis, monoiodoacetate, somatosensory processing, limb use, joint degeneration

Introduction

Osteoarthritis (OA) affects approximately 630 million people worldwide, or 15% of the global population, making it one of the most common long-term chronic diseases (Udgata, 2014). Osteoarthritis is a lifelong degenerative disease affecting all components of the joint, and it can be associated with pain. However, the relationship between measurable disease and pain is complex and nonlinear (Neogi, 2013). Joint pain and arthritis account for 58% of all painful conditions, significantly contributing to the economic burden of persistent pain (Gaskin and Richard, 2012). Persistent joint pain can interfere with a person's quality of life by impairing mobility, the ability to perform activities of daily living, and also creating anxiety, cognitive dysfunction, and impaired mood (e.g., depression). Current options for pain management in OA patients is considered suboptimal (Vinatier et al., 2016), and translational pain research is not producing novel, effective, and safe therapeutic options (Burgess and Williams, 2010). There has been quite a lot of discussion recently about how to optimize translational pain research in this area (Lascelles et al., 2018; Malfait and Little, 2015; Mogil, 2019a; Mogil, 2019b).

Induced rodent models of OA are critically important to the discovery of novel therapeutics, and they are used to assess both putative disease modifying agents, and putative analgesics. To date, there is not agreement on one gold standard experimental rodent model of OA. Both surgical and chemical models of OA in rodents have shown great value in studying disease pathways, mechanisms, and treatment targets (Malfait and Little, 2015). The intraarticular injection of monoiodoacetate (MIA) is a well-established and the most widely used OA model in mice and rodents to study alterations in sensory thresholds, functional impairment in limb use, cartilage degeneration, and novel therapies (Combe et al., 2004; Ferreira-Gomes et al., 2012; Jacobs et al., 2017; Marker and Pomonis, 2012). The MIA model produces rapid, reliable, and synchronous OA lesions and associated hypersensitivity and pain without surgical intervention (Gerwin et al., 2010; Wang et al., 2016). This chemical model resembles human degenerative OA by replicating pain-associated impairments and histological degeneration (Fernihough et al., 2004; Ferreira-Gomes et al., 2012; Nagase et al., 2012). Surgical models, such as the destabilization of the medial meniscus (DMM), cause slow and progressive site-specific articular cartilage degeneration, osteophytes, and subchondral bone defects in the medial tibial plateaus of the stifle (Iijima et al., 2014; Loeser et al., 2013). Despite numerous studies employing rodent OA models, none have compared different models in rodent across clinical alterations (e.g., reflexive, non-reflexive) and histological characteristics. Therefore, the objective of this study was to compare and contrast the clinical pain-associated alterations and histological disease severity across chemical (i.e., MIA) and surgical (i.e., DMM model, and the combined DMM and anterior cruciate ligament (ACL) transection) models of OA in the rodent. We hypothesized the surgical OA models would have greater pain-associated changes and more localized, slowly progressive, and less severe OA lesions than the chemical OA model.

Materials and Methods

Sprague Dawley rodents (n=50; 8-10 weeks old and 278-373 g at beginning of experiments; SAS CrI:SD; Charles River, Kingston, NY) were used for this study. All rodents were acclimated to the laboratory for at least one week prior to the start of experiments. Rodents were housed 2 per cage in standard rodent cages with food and water available *ad libitum* and kept on a standard 12:12 light/dark cycle. The cages were housed in temperature (19-24°C) and humidity (55 ± 15%) conditioned rooms. All rodents were clinically healthy prior to the study, and vendor health reports confirmed that the colony was free of recognized pathogens. Estrus cycles were not monitored. Prior to initiation of the studies, the available rodents were randomized and assigned to injury groups.

Induction of OA Models

For all procedures described below, rodents were anesthetized using inhalation anesthesia (O₂: 1.5-2 L/min; Isoflurane: 1.5-2.5%) and were visually monitored until recovery. After baseline values were determined, the OA models were established. Following injection of the irritant or surgical procedure, rodents were placed in their home cage and allowed to recover. The MIA and ACL+DMM groups were then tested at pre-determined intervals for clinical metrics and all three OA groups were used for histology.

For induction of arthritis with MIA, a single percutaneous intraarticular injection of 2 mg of MIA (Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA) or saline vehicle through the infrapatellar ligament of the left stifle joint (n=22 and 14, respectively) as previously described (Guingamp et al., 1997). MIA was dissolved in physiological saline and administered in 25 µL using a 0.3mL 30-gauge 0.5 inch needle insulin syringe. Saline-injected rodents (S) received equal volumes. The right contralateral stifle joint was used as a behavioral and histologic control.

Subjective Assessments of Overall Health

Body weight was recorded weekly for the duration of the study. Changes in body weight from baseline were calculated as an indirect assessment of health status and appetite.

Limb Use Analysis

Rodents were habituated to the behavioral testing suite for at least 30 minutes before testing. Dynamic gait was evaluated before static weight-bearing with at least a 30 minute rest period between testing. Baseline readings for all testing were established prior to the induction of OA then evaluated weekly for the duration of the study. Each rodent's right (contralateral) hindpaw served as its control.

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis was performed by using computer software (JMP®, Version 14.0. SAS Institute Inc., Cary, NC). The Wilcoxon Rank Sums test or Steel-Dwass method were used to analyze the difference between means of two or more independent groups, respectively, and to analyze multiple comparisons. All assessments were evaluated as independent measures.

The critical P value was automatically corrected for the numbers of multiple comparisons being made. A P-value of less than 0.05 was considered significant. Data were expressed as mean ± SEM.

Results

Clinical Evaluation

Rodents recovered uneventfully after either MIA injection or ACL+DMM surgery. The surgical incision healed within a few days with no complications; hair grew back within a week. Interestingly, body weight was unaffected in all groups (p>0.268), despite differences in measurable indicators of pain. However, a group by time interaction was detected within all groups gradually gaining weight over time (p<0.001).

4.0.1 Subjective Lameness

Overall, rodents in both the MIA and ACL+DMM groups appeared visually lame for 28 and 42 days, respectively, and were significantly more lame than saline controls (p<0.001). Greater lameness scores were reported in ACL+DMM rodents compared to the MIA group (p<0.001). No changes in lameness were reported in saline control rodents (p=0.313). A group by time interaction was detected in both OA models (p<0.01), but ACL+DMM lameness scores were persistently higher than MIA scores for the duration of the study, and significantly so from D14 to D42 (Figure 1).

Reflexive Responses after OA Induction

Electronic von Frey (Mechanical Evoked Stimulus)

Overall the ipsilateral hindlimb was more sensitive than the contralateral hindlimb (p<0.049; 34.6 ± 0.7g vs. 36.7 ± 0.7g, respectively) following OA induction. Comparing the change from baseline in PWT for the ipsilateral hindlimb across models, there were no overall group by PWT interactions detected (p=0.706; Appendix B- Supplemental Figure 1a). When investigating the effects of time, there was a time effect in PWT for the ACL+DMM group (p=0.035) where progressively became more

sensitive to mechanical stimuli with peak hypersensitivity at D15 ($p=0.044$), and then remained below baseline until D43 but not significantly so (Appendix B- Supplemental Figure 1b). Significant acute mechanical hypersensitivity was found at D8 in the MIA ($p=0.017$) with a quick return towards baseline by D15. There were no significant changes in mechanical thresholds in the saline control group. These data suggest that ACL+DMM may have a slower but more persistent effect on mechanical somatosensory processing.

Hargreaves Plantar Test (Thermal Evoked Stimulus)

There was an overall group by PWL interaction detected following OA induction ($p=0.041$), with an overall trend towards thermal hypersensitivity in MIA model compared to saline ($p=0.061$), though not significantly so (Appendix B- Supplemental Figure 1c). Rodents in the MIA group slowly became more sensitive to thermal stimuli on their ipsilateral hindlimb by D15, though not significantly so ($p=0.087$), and then slowly returned to baseline by D36 (Appendix B- Supplemental Figure 1d). Changes in thermal sensitivity were not detected in the ACL+DMM group nor saline controls. These data suggest MIA has a negative effect on thermal (hot) sensitivity, which is different to the mechanical sensitivity data, suggesting differential effects of the OA model on sensory systems.

Effect of OA-Induced Changes on Dynamic Limb Use and Static Hindlimb Weight- Bearing

Significant histological evidence of stifle joint degeneration was seen in the ipsilateral hindlimb 43 days post-OA induction (regardless of model) when compared to the contralateral hindlimb ($p<0.001$), which had minimal to no damage across models. Both surgical and chemical OA models resulted in substantial damage to the medial tibial plateaus of the ipsilateral joint; however, the MIA model resulted in greater histopathological OA lesions based on modified Mankin, Pritzker, and Gerwin scoring systems (Figure 3). The histological scores were higher in the DMM model compared to the ACL+DMM model though not significantly so (Figure 3). When compared to the medial tibial plateaus, the lateral tibial plateaus had less pathological lesions across all models though not significantly so ($p=0.188$; data not shown). These findings demonstrate the MIA model produces profound, generalized cartilage degeneration within the weight-bearing surface of the joint leading to chondrocyte death, erosion of hyaline cartilage, mineralization of cartilage and bone, and destruction to tidemark integrity compared to surgical models. Furthermore, MIA damage extends further across the medial tibial plateaus and into the subchondral bone compared to the more localized lesions in the surgical models. These data suggest the DMM model may produce more OA-associated cartilage lesions compared to the combined ACL+DMM model.

Figure 1: Comparison of lameness scores across OA models.

Bar plot comparing the (a) overall lameness scores and line graph of the (b) lameness at each time point post-OA induction (x-axis). Groups represented as: ACL+DMM, blue; MIA, red; Saline control, black. Data are expressed as the mean $\pm$ SEM. * $p<0.05$, ** $p<0.01$, *** $p<0.001$ compared to baseline; $\wedge p<0.05$, $\wedge\wedge p<0.01$, $\wedge\wedge\wedge p<0.001$ compared to saline; $\phi p<0.05$, $\phi\phi p<0.01$, $\phi\phi\phi p<0.001$ for ACL+DMM vs MIA.

Figure 3: Histological scoring of cartilage damage 6 weeks following OA induction. Graphical representation of histological grading of ipsilateral stifle damage to medial tibial plateaus for ACL+DMM, MIA, saline control, and DMM rodents compare scoring methods: (a) Pritzker OARSI scores, (b) Modified Mankin score; and (c) Gerwin OARSI scores. Groups represented as: ACL+DMM, blue (circle); MIA, red (square); Saline control, black (triangle); DMM, grey (diamond). Data are expressed as the mean $\pm$ SEM. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$ for group comparisons.

Figure 4: Medial aspect of femorotibial joint sections stained with Safranin-O. Representative histologic images of the femorotibial joint from (a) saline controls 6 weeks after intra-articular injection, (b) ACL+DMM model 6 weeks post-surgical induction, (c) MIA model 6 weeks after intra-articular injection, and (d) DMM model 14 weeks post- surgical procedure. Ulceration of articular cartilage and loss of Safranin-O stain on the medial tibial plateau (arrow), complete loss of articular cartilage and extensive bone remodeling (bracket) are observed. Scale bar = 200 μ m. 10x magnification.

Discussion

The prevalence of stifle OA has approximately doubled since the middle of the 20th century (Wallace et al., 2017), and this has driven a greater emphasis on the development of treatments to modulate the disease progression and/or mitigate the OA-associated pain. As the translational process fails to produce novel and effective treatments for pain (Burgess and Williams, 2010), there is a greater focus on the preclinical models and associated outcome measures being used. In this study, we found that the induction of OA using the MIA model caused significantly more cartilage destruction in the medial aspect of the stifle joint than the surgical models; however, overall, rodents in the ACL+DMM model showed persistent signs of gait impairment as assessed visually and objectively. Reflexive measures were conflicting between modalities within the ACL+DMM group, with the ACL+DMM model producing greater mechanical hypersensitivity and greater thermal hyposensitivity compared to other groups, although not significantly so. The MIA model triggered mechanical and thermal hypersensitivity, but only significantly so with thermal stimulation compared to the saline group.

In experimental rodent models of OA, quantitative sensory testing, or evoked-stimuli responses, have been the gold standard to assess 'pain' induced by OA. In this study, overall, mechanical sensitivity was not significantly different between the OA groups and the saline control groups. However, the ACL+DMM surgery and MIA injection triggered significant mechanical hypersensitivity at D15 and D8, respectively, which was short-lasting. The overall lack of mechanical hypersensitivity in this study is unusual, since most experimental OA models demonstrate long-lasting mechanical sensitivity for at least 35 days (Fernihough et al., 2004; Im et al., 2010) or up to 15 weeks post-OA induction (Tsai et al., 2018). A recent

study reported a biphasic pattern of mechanical hypersensitivity, where sensitivity is greatest immediately (D1-5) and chronically (3-12 weeks) following surgical induction of OA (i.e., medial meniscal transection) (Temp et al., 2019). The reason for the dissimilarity seen between this study and others is unclear; however, may be related to different experimental protocols (e.g. models, assays), study design, or environmental factors.

The MIA model generated significant thermal hypersensitivity compared to the saline group, while rodents in the ACL+DMM group became less sensitive, although not significantly so, suggesting differential effects of the OA model on somatosensory systems. Similar to these findings, the literature on thermal sensitivity in rodent OA models has shown differing effects across models. Generally, there is a strong association with thermal hypersensitivity in chemical models of OA (Lee et al., 2009; Liu et al., 2011; Sluka et al., 1994), while in surgical models of OA there are no differences in thermal latencies detected (Balaganur et al., 2014; Barbosa et al., 2019; Bove et al., 2006; Temp et al., 2019; Tsai et al., 2018). Intra-articular injection of MIA in the stifle joint caused thermal hyperalgesia 28 days following injection (Liu et al., 2011). Varying effects of naturally occurring OA pain on thermal sensitivity (hyposensitivity and hypersensitivity) have also been found in canine (Hunt et al., 2019; Knazovicky et al., 2016; Williams et al., 2014) and human OA patients (Kosek and Ordeberg, 2000; Lee et al., 2011).

Limitations of quantitative sensory tests include the varying and unpredictable effects of the experimenter, environment, and exact experiment conditions. However, another important limitation of reflex measures is that they are measures of changes in sensitivity, and do not reflect the aversive nature of pain (the affective components) (Huang et al., 2019). Measures of more complex behaviors, including the ability to perform activities, are likely better measures of the aversive nature of pain. Similarly, measures of limb use in relation to joint disease likely more closely reflect pain itself.

Visual lameness was observed for 6-week period, with persistently worse scores in the ACL+DMM group compared to the MIA group. Interestingly, the degree of lameness did not correlate with the severity of joint damage, as the MIA group had higher histological scores than ACL+DMM group. This underscores the poor relationship between measurable disease and pain seen in clinical cases (Finan et al., 2013). As discussed later, the objective measures of limb use did not show such pronounced changes.

Patients with stifle OA have an increase in biomechanical adduction therefore have higher mechanical loads on the medial compartment of stifle, which significantly contributes to OA progression (Tateuchi, 2019). Similar characteristics may occur with joint instability caused by the ACL+DMM surgical procedure. Although biomechanics were not directly measured in this study, we measured functional limb use during ambulation and while standing. Gait was significantly altered in both OA-induction models compared to controls, characterized by: reduction in print length, print area, and stance and longer swing phase of the ipsilateral hindlimb. Additionally, static weight-bearing was negatively impacted by OA causing the injured hindlimb to have a reduction in weight-bearing. Significant dynamic and static limb disability was short-lasting with peak dysfunction detected the day after OA- induction, comparable to other studies (Adaes et al., 2015; Angeby Moller et al., 2018; Temp et al., 2019). Swing time was significantly greater in ipsilateral hindlimbs injected with MIA compared to controls and this effect was reversed with COX-2 inhibitors (Ferland et al., 2011).

Additionally, similar changes to gait and weight-bearing have been found in canine (Brown et al., 2013; Little et al., 2016; Seibert et al., 2012) and humans with OA (Messier, 1994; Tateuchi, 2019). One of the most common characteristic changes in human stifle OA patients is an increased stride time during ambulation (Tateuchi, 2019). The ACL+DMM model had more persistent effects on gait and static weight bearing when compared to MIA models, although not significantly so. These data are corroborated by the subjective lameness scores, which were significantly higher in the ACL+DMM model compared to MIA model. The greater effects on limb use in the ACL+DMM model may have been due to greater pain, however joint instability may also have

contributed to this. The MIA model does not directly cause instability. Similar changes occur in human patients with hip OA and stifle OA, where instability alters gait and stance (Tateuchi, 2019).

Six week following intra-articular injection of MIA, severe chondrocyte death, erosion of the hyaline cartilage, and remodeling of the subchondral bone was observed. Previous reports have found these characteristics as well as the presence of osteophytes, osteolysis, and edema (Ferland et al., 2011; Guingamp et al., 1997; Pomonis et al., 2005). Substantial cartilage degeneration has been detected as early as 14 days following MIA injection (Ma et al., 2018). Comparatively, joint degeneration in the MIA model was significantly worse than the ACL+DMM model, assessed at the same time point, and the DMM model, evaluated 14 weeks following OA-induction. The ACL+DMM model produced minimal pathological changes with similar histological scores to the saline controls. The predominant features in the ACL+DMM model were superficial surface discontinuity and occasional cell proliferation in the medial tibial plateau. Other studies using surgical models of OA found similar lesions at 4 and 6 weeks but substantial cartilage degeneration, similar to what was found in the MIA model in this study, at more chronic periods (e.g. 12 weeks) were demonstrated (Hayami et al., 2006; Karahan et al., 2001; Lorenz and Grassel, 2014; Temp et al., 2019). Interestingly, compared to mouse studies, there is a paucity of information in the literature on the progression of OA in the rodent ACL+DMM model and more so in the rodent DMM model, which may be due to the fact that minimal lesions occur. This was in agreement with our hypothesis that the surgical OA models would have a slower progression of OA damage due to the localized damage caused by joint instability following the surgical manipulation.

Conclusion

In summary, our histological analysis and clinical evaluation of pain for 6 weeks following ACL+DMM or MIA OA-induction demonstrated similarities to human stifle OA, including substantial cartilage destruction, mechanical hypersensitivity, and reduced dynamic and static limb use. The ACL+DMM models may be more valuable in pain studies specifically investigating changes in pain behaviors as these were generally slightly more persistent in the assays evaluated here. Alternatively, the MIA model may be a more suitable model for quickly screening novel therapeutics targeted towards mitigating or reversing histological changes associated with OA as there was substantial cartilage degeneration within a 6 weeks period. Future studies should investigate the progression of these surgical models over a longer time-course as well as assess reflexive and non-reflexive pain behaviors in the DMM surgical model, which may be a clinically relevant rodent OA model for pain studies.

4.1 References

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